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GUILLAIN-BARRE SINDROMI VA UNI TASHXISLASHGA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUV

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Guillain-Barre (Giyen-Barre) sindromi (GBS)-periferik nerv sistemasining yallig'lanish kasalligi bo'lib, o'tkir bo'shashgan falajlikning eng keng tarqalgan sababi bo'lib, yillik global kasallanish taxmin erkaklarda ayollarga qaraganda tez-tez uchraydi va kasallanish bemor yoshi kattalashishi bilan ortadi, ammo barcha yosh guruhlariga ta'sir qilishi mumkin .GBS bilan og'riqan bemorlar odatda oyoqlarda qo'llar va kranial mushaklarga o'tadigan zaiflik va hissiy belgilar bilan namoyon bo'ladilar, garchi kasallikning klinik ko'rinishi geterogen bo'lsa-da va bir nechta aniq klinik variantlar mavjud. GBS patogenezi to'liq tushunilmagan bo'lsa-da, periferik nervlarning shikastlanishiga olib keladigan infeksiyalarga noadekvat immun javobidan kelib chiqadi deb taxmin qilinadi.GBS bilan og'riqan bemorlarning kichik guruhida gangliozidlarga qarshi antitanalar topiladi, ular aksollemma va periferik nervlarning boshqa tarkibiy qismlarida yuqori zichlikda joylashganbo'ladi. GBSkasallikni qo'zg'atadigan yuqumli kasalliklar epidemiyasi paytida ortishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: *Guillain-Barre (Giyen-Barre) sindromi, Poliradikulonevropatiya, Miller Fisher sindromi, Bickerstaff miya ustuni ensefaliti, o'tkir ko'ndalang miyelit, Miyasteniya Gravis, Lambert Eaton miyastenik sindromi, COVID-19, AAN, BCC, NINDS, plazmoferez.*

Dolzarbli: GBS bilan kasallangan bemorlarning ko'pchiligi 2 hafta ichida maksimal nogironlik qayd etiladi. GBS bilan og'rikan bemorlarning taxminan 20 foizi nafas olish yetishmovchiligini rivojlanadi va suniy o'pka ventilyatsiyasi talab qilinadi. Aritmiyalar va qon bosimining beqarorligi avtonom nerv tizimining ishtiroki tufayli yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Avtonom nerv tizimining bunday javobi 3-10% hollarda o'linga sabab bo'ladi. Dastlabki progressiv bosqichdan so'ng, GBS bilan og'rikan bemorlarda bir necha kundan haftalar yoki oylargacha davom etishi mumkin bo'lgan plato bosqichiga kuzatiladi, shundan so'ng ular tuzalishni boshlaydilar va GBS bilan og'rikan bemorlarning 60-80%i kasallik boshlanganidan 6 oy o'tgach, mustaqil ravishda yura oladilar. Autoimmun kasalliklarning chastotasi COVID-19 pandemiyasidan so'ng sezilarlidirajada oshdi. COVID-19 pandemiyasigacha har 100,000 aholiga 2-4 bemor to'g'ri kelgan, COVID-19 dan keyin bemorlar soni 100,000 aholiga 7-9 ga to'g'ri keladi. GBS ni to'g'ri tashxislash qiyinchilik tug'diradi. Tashxisning to'g'ri qo'yilishi va rejali davolash taktikasini amalga oshirish ijobiy natija bilan yakunlashni kafolatlaydi.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari: Ilmiy izlanish 2019-2023-yillarda Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi ko'p tarmoqli klinikasi Nevrologiya bo'limi va RSHTYIM Jizzax filialidada o'tkazildi. Tadqiqot davomida GBS bilan kasallangan 20 bemor o'rganildi. Bemorlarning 12tasi (60%) ayollar, 8tasi (40%) erkaklar bo'lib ularning yosh diapazoni 15-65 yoshni tashkil qiladi. Bemorlarning barchasida qonning umumiy va biokimyoviy tahlili, ENMG, lumbal punksiya o'tkazildi va ularning nevrologik va psixologik statusi tekshirildi. Bemorlarni tashxislashda "NINDS" (National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke), "AAN" (American Academy of Neurology), BCC diagnostik kriteriyalariga asoslanildi.

Natija: Bemorlarning laborator ko'rsatkichlari quyidagicha: umumiy qon tahlilida leykoysitoz $10-25 \times 10^9/l$ oralig'ida (90%), EChT oshishi 18-40mm/soat oralig'ida (75%) kuzatildi. Qonning biokimyoviy tahlilida C reaktiv oqsil 10ml/dl dan oshishi (70%) holatda kuzatiladi. Lumbal punksiyada albumin-sitologik dissosatsiya aniqlandi (85%).

“NINDS” kriteriyalaribo‘yicha natijalar:

1-guruh belgilar (progressiv bilateral simmetrik yuqoriga ko‘tariluvchi parez(para,tetraparez), bilateral pay reflexlarining yo‘qolishi yoki pasayishi) 100 % bemorlarda uchradi,

2-guruh belgilar (progressiv fazaning 4-haftadan oshmasligi, belgilarning simmetrikligi, sensor belgilarning qo‘shilishi, kranial nervlarning parezi,autonomik disfunksiya, muscular,radicular og‘riqlar, CSF da oqsil miqdorining oshishi, elektrodiagnostikada o‘tkazuvchanlikning sekinlashishi) 80% bemorlarda uchradi.

3-guruh belgilar (CSF da pleositoz darajasi $50 \times 10^6/l$ dan oshishi, belgilarning asimmetrikligi, 24 kundan ortiq progressiya, giperreflexia va klonus uchrashi, o‘tkir og‘riqlar(miyelitnikiga o‘xshash), Abdominal og‘riqlar, sekin progressiya, kognitiv buzilishlar) 5% bemorlarda uchradi.

“BCC” bo‘yicha GBS ning 6 ta darajasi mavjud bo‘lib, ilmiy izlanish davomida quyidagilar qayd qilindi:

5% bemorda 1-daraja (uzoq masofaga yugurganda belgilar yuzaga chiqadi), 15% bemorlarda 2-daraja (belgilar 10 m va undan ortiq yurganda yuzagachiqadi), 20% bemorlarda 3-daraja (10 m gacha yurganda yordamga muhtoj bo‘ladi), 40% bemorlarda 4-daraja (yura olmaydi(xuddi bog‘langan insondek)), 15% bemorlarda 5 daraja (kunning malum bir qismida ventilatsiyaga muhtoj),5% bemorlarda 6 daraja (to‘liq(total) plegiya).

Tekshiruvlar natijasida aniqlangan bemorlarda quyidagi subtiplar qayd etildi: - klassik sensori-motor GBS-50%(10 bemor), faqat motor genezli (AMAN)-20%(4 bemor), Miller Fisher sindromi-10% (2 bemor), paraparetik -10%(2 bemor), PhCB (pharyngeal-cervical-brachial)-5%(1 bemor), faqat sensor genezli-5%(1bemor). Differensial tashxislashda “AAN” kriteriyasiga asoslanildi.

Xulosa: Kasallikning erta aniqlanishi davolash samaradorligini oshirib, nogironlik va o‘lim xolatlarining oldi olinadi. Kasallik 1-haftada aniqlanib “BBC” kriteriyasi bo‘yicha 0,1,2,3 darajalari darhol davolash (plazmafarez) choralari ko‘rilsa nogironlik holati kuzatilmaydi. Tashxis qo‘yishning kechikishi bemorlarda nogironlik va o‘lim holatlarining ortishiga olib keladi.

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